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Synthesis of spirochromene derivatives catalyzed by Mn(bpyo)₂/MCM-41 in water

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Abstract

A three-component one-pot synthesis of spirochromene derivatives by condensing cyclic 1,3-diketones, isatin or acenaphthenequinone, and malononitrile using a catalytic amount of Mn(bpyo)₂/MCM-41 in refluxing water is reported.

Keyword

Mn(bpyo)₂/MCM-41, Multi-component one-pot reaction, Reaction in water, Spirochromene.